

International Society for Biocuration response to NIH RFI on Proposed Provisions for a Draft Data Management and Sharing Policy for NIH Funded or Supported Research

Section I: The definition of Scientific Data

Any information generated as a result of a scientific experiment, i.e. a collection or single item of factual information, derived from measurement or research, from which conclusions may be drawn (Reference: NCIT:C25474). Data may be either raw, or subsequently further processed but both as of value. If data has been further processed, how this was performed should be made clear when made publicly available.

Section II: The requirements for Data Management and Sharing Plans

Data management and sharing plans should include details of public domain repositories through which the data will be made available, the data standards which will be adopted when preparing the data for database deposition and a clear statement of accompanying information (meta-data) that will be included to ensure that the data is reusable by the scientific community. Interim/final reports should track the progress of such depositions and include citation of accession numbers when a deposition has been accepted by a public domain repository. The NIH should publish lists of trusted core data repositories that are appropriate for each data type and are stably funded, to ensure long-term maintenance of this data. This should include the provision of biocurators who will ensure data meets the required standard. The Provisions should include a requirement that data be licensed under one of the recognized open data licenses at <https://opendefinition.org/licenses/>, or an explanation of why such a license cannot be adopted. All data and metadata necessary to reproduce analyses and results in publications should be released at the time of publication, for the purposes of both reproducibility and secondary analysis.

Section III: The optimal timing, including possible phased adoption, for NIH to consider in implementing various parts of a new data management and sharing policy and how possible phasing could relate to needed improvements in data infrastructure, resources, and standards

Identifying, and actively supported, selected core resources will be critical for this initiative to have long-term sustainability. The NIH should publish a continually-updated list of compliant data repositories for each data type. NIH should also develop and publish specific criteria by which repositories can qualify as "NIH-compliant". Those criteria can address issues like data preservation plans, issuance of stable DOIs, API access, etc. NIH should be part of a global mechanism to financially support repositories that are not created/maintained by NIH itself.

For data types with no established data repository, grantees should be strongly encouraged or required to utilize a general purpose data repository (like Harvard Dataverse, Figshare, Data Dryad, GigaDB, etc.).